

**THE ROLE OF THE VILLAGE CHIEF
IN GOVERNANCE OF SIRON OLONG VILLAGE,
KALIMANTAN PROVINCE, INDONESIA**

**Yulfianus Berthu,
Saladin Galib,
Jamaluddinⁱ**

Master of Government Science,
Lambung Mangkurat University,
Indonesia

Abstract:

Village head has the main task of creating a democratic life, encouraging community development and provide good public services. The role of the village head is very important for the governance of the village, contributing to realize a good administration. This study aims to determine and analyze which is the role of village chief of Olong Siron in realizing a good governance. The research used a qualitative descriptive approach. Data were collected by interview, observation and documentation; the key informants were the Tanah Siang district head, the village head of Olong Siron, the chairman Olong Desa Siron BPD, the secretary Olong Desa Siron and other community leaders. The results showed that the role of the village head Olong Siron in realizing good governance was good enough. The main investigated aspects were participation, fair application of law, transparency, vision strategy, orientation, justice, effectiveness, accountability, responsiveness, and interdependence in all aspect. The participation rate was increasingly wide spreading and the decision-making was effective.

Keywords: public services, public participation, governance

1. Introduction

Another goal of regional autonomy is to empower the region by increasing the community participation. Community involvement in local government provides opportunities for people to choose leaders democratically and build trust between the community and the government (Haryadi, 2018). Implementation of the development program and choosing the next priorities between education, health, environmental management and community empowerment must be fulfilled. Arranging the spirit of

ⁱ Correspondence: email jurnalulm@gmail.com

development today is not balanced by a real effort to improve the welfare of the community (Widjaja, 2003).

Rural development comprises activities taking place in the village and it covers all the aspects of communities' life. Mobilizing communities to participate in the development, successful implementation of government affairs and rural progress are largely determined by the establishment of the village government in an efficient and effective manner. Therefore, we realize that in the process of rural development, planning, direct community involvement at every stage of development are the village start of the organizing process; implementation and continuation are the keys to the success of development itself (Haryadi, 2018).

When physical and non-physical development is not balanced, how can a portion of citizens who are in the bottom layer enjoy a high-profile development? (Court, 1996) To provide a balance between developments, the autonomy is necessary. Regional autonomy is given in form of democracy, justice, equity and diversity. The purpose of giving autonomy to the regions is comprised on the enactment on Law no. 23 of 2014 regarding the local government, which states that the regional administration is directed to accelerate the realization of public welfare by improving services, empowerment and community participation.

One fundamental problem in the administration of government at the central, regional and village levels is to build governmental mechanisms that can carry out the mission of realizing a prosperous society. The government must carry out the development based on the aspirations of society and provide public services as well as possible. The role of the public and the private sector is an important key in developing democracy. Active participation, freedom, and openness of the opinion and accountability of governance are the primary means for a country, the private sector and communities to work together to build democracy and governance better (Lamangida, Akbar and Hasan, 2017).

The village government is the executive department of government's vision of development of a harmonious life in the village. To be able to perform its role effectively and efficiently, the village government (village head) should follow the progress of rural communities and the surrounding environment. The village is led by the chief, as the supreme leader who must master the development activities.

The success of governance and community development at the village level is determined by the ability of leaders in directing society. Olong Desa Siron is a village located in the district during the ground the Murung Kingdom, Central Kalimantan province where the indigenous population is Dayak.

The head of Siron Olong has a role of deciding the duties and functions independently. He also takes manages the forest according to the local socio-cultural conditions. Rural development includes the management of the village administration, where the village head had a role in it. Kepala Desa Siron Olong have a very large role in promoting development in Olong Siron village as well as a facilitator in increasing community involvement in rural development. It is expected that any community can

enjoy and can keep the fruits this kind of village administration (Widjaja, 2003; Kartasasmita, 1996).

2. Research Methods

The research approach used in this study was a descriptive approach. Descriptive research is a study that aims to describe a situation or phenomenon that occurs currently by using scientific procedures to address the actual problem (Sarman, 2004; Sugiyono, 2012). It can be said that the descriptive research method is a method used to describe, interpret, based on the existing relationship, opinions developed by using scientific procedures to address the actual problem. This research was conducted in the village of Olong Siron.

Collection techniques used were as follows:

- observation, to see and explore the role of the chief in promoting development in the village highway,
- interviews, as the data collection process with the debriefing and meeting face to face by researchers and respondents using your interview (interview guidelines) and depth interviews,
- documentation, in a written form of the collection of objects such as books, journals, archives, personal documents, and official documents related parties.

Miles and Huberman models have been used for data analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

Head of Desa Siron Olong is the supreme leader and head of government at the village level. Therefore, the village head is fully responsible for the wheels of government in the village. Kepala Desa Siron Olong acts as guardian, protector and community coach. Also, the village chief in charge of conducting government affairs, and in implementing rural development in the region. He is a development planner, construction supervisor, and pioneer in the development.

Development is an effort to improve people's lives by using existing resources. Development leads to the changes and improvements, towards welfare-oriented advancement and prosperity of society. Whereas, rural development comprises the development activities taking place in the village, it covers all aspects of society and is done by self-help cooperation. The aim is to improve the welfare of rural communities based on the capabilities and potential of natural resources (SDA) them through improved quality of life, skills and community initiatives. Rural development has the meaning of building rural communities by prioritizing aspects of community needs (Lamangida, Akbar, & Hasan, 2017).

Siron Olong's village head has carried out its role as administrator of development to motivate people to participate in building the village. Kepala Desa Siron Olong function is helping to grow and expand cooperation, to realize the

implementation of community development that has been planned in the budget of the village. This means that the village head as the leader in the village is the organizer and the person in charge in the fields of government, development and society.

Guidance and coaching can be defined as a series of activities or processes meant to maintain, preserve, and promote the organization. One decision made together with the village head Olong Desa Siron by BPD is to formulate and establish budget village (APBDes). In the decision-making process, there are two kinds of decisions:

- social decisions, which binds the community voluntarily without clear sanctions,
- formal decisions, made by villages and set up to perform the functions of decision making.

The shape of the first kind of decisions is often found in the social life of the village, the decision-making process is done through a process of mutual agreement, whereas previously the reason for selection of alternatives outlined in advance by the parent/community leaders and youth organizations in the village. The shape of the second kind of decisions is based on procedures that have been agreed, such as the process of village development forum (musrenbangdes) done once a year.

All rural development programs are proposed or discussed by forum Planning Meeting of Rural Development (musrenbangdes) which serves as a forum to generate agreement and understanding among development actors about RKP and RPKD focuses on discussions to synchronize the work plan between work units of government and society in the achievement regional development objectives. In musrenbangdes, implementation will be attended by all village, BPD members, community leaders, indigenous, youth and was also attended by district and county governments, with the aim that all development planning and development can be accommodated evenly.

The closeness of the relationship between the head of the village and rural communities can influence the knowledge and understanding of the village head of the needs of rural communities. Interaction and communication between village leaders and villagers, providing a sense of camaraderie and kinship which make people feel very concerned by the village administration. Therefore, the village chief must be able to perform the duties, obligations and functions as the leader. The effort to create good governance must be preceded by the application of the principles of good governance Village head became a major factor in the application of these principles to achieve good governance.

In the village Olong Siron, the governance confronted with various obstacles. In particular, for the new society is quite difficult to get good service, as well as the paperwork, the slow performance of village officials in responding properly. But until now, the service provided by the village head of Olong Siron is carrying out its role to achieve a better governance.

A. Society participation

The ability of the village head to motivate people to participate in development is very important; in that way the development programs can be run following the plan that

had been developed previously jointly between the government and society. Community participation is necessary for its common goals, for achieving well-being in the community and for creating democracy in the country. With the participation of the community, the village is moving forward, in terms of economic, social and political.

In general, the people participate if they feel the activity is important for them. Community involvement through the support of the implementation embodied the community through their support for each project/development activities carried out in the environment around them.

B. Law Enforcement

Enforcement is the legal framework for a fair and implemented indiscriminate community development. The framework is including laws regarding human rights. Law is a very important factor for a good governance. Shortcomings of legal system greatly affects the overall performance of the government. Certainly, good governance will not run smoothly over a weak legal system. The village head of Olong Siron will give strict punishment to the people who are not respecting the law.

C. Transparency

Transparency is a principle that guarantees access or freedom for every person to obtain information about governance, information on the policy-making, implementation process and the results achieved. Transparency is one of the factors that encourages good governance, provide information regarding the implementation of development, and use of village funds to the public.

D. Strategic Vision

Strategic vision ensures a broad perspective good governance and human development, as well as on the required sensitivity to realize these developments. In addition, must exist an understanding of the complexity of the historical, cultural and social that became the basis for this perspective.

E. Orientation

In solving various problems in the community, the village head of Olong Siron, always put deliberation with a spirit of understanding. If there is a problem that involves the villagers, the village government need to deliberate with citizens and community leaders. In this case, the village chief of Olong Siron uses to get the community consensus, for example in the event musrengbangdesa. Musrengbangde gathers the villagers and government leaders to discuss rural development programs, rural policies and the use of village funds. Programs and implementation policies are made at the suggestion of the public administration.

F. Fairness and Effectiveness

Good governance provides equal opportunities to all its people, to both men and women, in their efforts to improve and maintain quality and efficiency of the public services. Siron Olong's village head together with BPD and Olong Siron village communities must prioritize the tasks which comes first for the benefit of community.

G. Accountability

Accountability is a manifestation of the obligations of a government agency to take responsibility for the success and the failure to implement the vision and mission, the implementation of accountability can also be done through a strategic approach that will accommodate the rapid changes in the organization and quickly adapt to changes that occur in anticipation to cope with the demands of the parties an interest in it.

H. Responsiveness

Responsiveness refers to the alignment between programs and activities with the needs of the community. Dilulio (1994) says that the responsiveness of the bureaucracy is the ability to recognize the service and develop programs according to the needs and aspirations of the community (Suwardianto, 2015). In short, it can be said that this measure bureaucratic responsiveness to the expectations, desires and aspirations and demands of service users. Responsiveness is needed in the public service because it is evidence of the ability of organizations to identify community needs.

I. Mutual Engagement

Overall characteristics of the above-mentioned good governance are mutually reinforcing and interrelated and can not stand alone. For example, information is more easily accessible, dutiful transparency the better, more comprehensive level of participation and decision-making make the process more effective. Wider participation contributes to the information exchange necessary information for decision-making, and to strengthen the validity or legitimacy of the decision or set. The level of legitimacy of a strong decision, in turn, promotes the effectiveness of its implementation, and encourages increased participation.

4. Conclusion

The role of the village chief of Olong Siron in realizing an effective governance can be assessed by considering the following aspects: community participation, application of laws fair in terms of public services and transparency; the village administration has to be run openly, so the public can control the performance of village officials. The responsiveness of the village head is quite active and responsive in terms of providing services and follow-up on complaints from Olong Siron villagers. Orientation to solve various problems that occur in the community environment, meaning a consensus deliberation based on a family spirit. A good justice governance provides equal

opportunities to all communities, both men and women in their efforts to improve and maintain their quality of life. The government must be effective and efficient in producing output in the form of rules, policies, development and public welfare.

The village head of Olong Siron together with the BPD and the community prioritize the development on the interests of the community. For implementing a good accountability, a report on the administration of the village is written at the end of the fiscal year and sent to Village Consultative Body (BPD) at the end of each year the budget. In addition, the strategic vision ensures a broad and far-reaching perspective on good governance and human development.

References

- Agung, Y. O. (1996). *Pengantar Ilmu Pariwisata*. Bandung: Angkasa Offset.
- Beratha, N. (1982). *Desa, Publik, Konsep, Teori dan Aplikasi*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
- Haryadi, D. (2018). *Peran Kepala Desa dalam Pelaksanaan Pembangunan Desa Pesisir*. Tanjungpinang: Universitas Maritim Raja Ali Haji (Program Studi Ilmu Pemerintahan Fakultas Ilmu Sosial Dan Politik).
- Kartasasmita, G. (1996). *Pembangunan untuk Rakyat: Memadukan Pertumbuhan dan Pemerataan*. Jakarta: CIDES.
- Lamangida, T., Akbar, M., & Hasan, H. (2017). Kepemimpinan Kepala Desa Dalam Membangun Desa Bandungrejo Kecamatan Boliyohuto. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Vol. 6, No. 1*, 68-78.
- Sarman, M. (2004). *Pengantar Metodologi Penelitian Sosial*. Pustaka Fisip Unlam: Banjarmasin.
- Sugiyono. (2012). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif Dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sukandarrumidi. (2002). *Metode Penelitian Petunjuk Praktis Untuk Peneliti Pemula*. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- Suwardianto, S. (2015). *Peranan kepala desa dalam pemberdayaan masyarakat di Desa Sidoagung Kecamatan Godean Kabupaten Sleman*. Program Studi Pendidikan Luar Sekolah. Yogyakarta: Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta (Jurusan Pendidikan Luar Sekolah Fakultas Ilmu Pendidikan).
- Widjaja. (2003). *Pemerintah Desa/Marga*. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Undang-Undang Nomor 23 tahun 2014 Tentang Pemerintahan Daerah
- Undang-Undang Nomor 6 Tahun 2014 tentang Desa
- Permendagri Nomor 114 Tahun 2014 tentang pedoman pembangunan Desa

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